

METHODOLOGY FOR THE APPLICATION OF PEDAGOGICAL AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT LEARNING OF STUDENTS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the methodology for applying pedagogical and information technologies in the organization of independent learning among students in general secondary schools.*

Keywords: *independent work, independent learning, educational resource, innovative technology, SMART education, mobility, presentation, methodology, presentation.*

INTRODUCTION.

It is important to highlight the fact that various means of information and communication technologies can be used for the effective organization of independent learning. In particular, electronic courses, electronic learning systems, video lectures, webinars, electronic tests, etc. In addition to these means, modern and compact mobile technologies are currently available. When organizing independent learning of students using mobile technologies, the educational material is first studied regardless of time and place. This allows you to obtain the information necessary for learning.

Over the years, pedagogical works, scientific sources devoted to educational technologies have brought educational technologies to a certain level. Our current task is to develop mobile educational technologies together with distance learning technologies in the context of a technological breakthrough and increased danger. In this regard, we decided to devote the main part of our article to electronic educational technologies.

Learning using mobile technologies is currently widely used in the education systems of foreign countries. It can be noted that in the USA, Canada and European countries, mobile educational technologies have been introduced into the teaching of various subjects through the use of a single platform combining mobile educational resources and methods for their development.

It is worth emphasizing the point that many companies producing computer, communication and computing equipment produce compact modern computers with touch screens on a new platform. These include tablets, smartphones and mobile devices. According to statistics from developed countries, mobile devices are most often smartphones or tablets, which are components of an intelligent system.

A touch screen is used to control the tablet. You work with it with your fingers, without using a physical keyboard and mouse. Entering text on a touch screen is usually not inferior to typing on a keyboard.

In the 70s of the 20th century, an American scientist in the field of computer theory Alan Key proposed the idea of a "book-sized computer". With the advent of pocket computers in the

90s, mobile learning projects and the use of mobile education for students appeared. The use of mobile technologies in the network was studied in detail in the research work of V.A. Kuklev.

DISCUSSION.

The research work reflects information on the use of distance learning in a wireless WiMAX network based on mobile devices and work on computers such as Intel Classmate for children. Also in the research work of M.A. Grigorieva the issues of teaching computer science on mobile computer systems, organization of teaching mathematics and linguistics on mobile systems in the projects of Savill-Smith, G. Stead and G. Colley were studied. Educational technologies based on domestic information and telecommunication means (mobile computer systems: phones, tablets, smartphones) are widely used in Australia, Great Britain, Italy, Canada, Cyprus, Mexico, New Zealand, Poland, USA, Turkey, Chile, Sweden, South Africa.

Due to the constant development of mobile devices, their widespread use as a means of education is becoming increasingly relevant in both traditional and non-traditional education. One of the modern teaching methods is mobile-based learning, which is developing every day. According to the analytical forecast of Infonetics Research, the number of people using the global network based on mobile communications has reached about 6 million over the past five years. Currently, the term "mobile education" can be used in three ways:

Mobile learning (M-learning) is a technology for obtaining and exchanging knowledge using mobile devices (phones or pocket computers) using WAP, GPRS or 3G technologies (the main one of which is the ability to access the Internet);

Mobile learning (M-learning) is a technology for organizing the educational process using mobile communication devices (mobile phones and communicators);

Mobile learning (M-learning) is a learning process that involves the use of personal learning devices (laptops, pocket computers or mobile phones) in a remote mode.

There are many conferences and exhibitions on the topic of mobile learning. These include mlearn, WMUTE and IADIS Mobile, ISML in Jordan, mobile learning in Malaysia, working with handheld devices in London and mobile learning in the USA. The main question raised in the conferences was to what extent mobile learning affects student learning. The importance of mobile learning is as follows:

- it allows the use of new technologies in education;
- mobile devices are compact and smaller in size compared to books, computers and other devices;
- can be used by students participating in learning.

Mobile devices are not only designed to make calls or exchange messages but also to perform a wider range of tasks. Today, these devices provide many users with the ability to obtain information, build knowledge and share ideas. Indeed, today there are many definitions of mobile education or mobile learning. These tools remain one of the main tools for students to obtain information. Students want to have educational resources on their smartphones or tablets at all times.

It should be taken into consideration that the number of Internet connections via mobile technologies has increased several times compared to personal and laptop computers. According to experts, when analyzing the services provided by mobile operators, it is noted that if earlier mobile communications were used only for communication, now the demand for Internet communication instead of conversations is growing. Practice shows that students' attempts to use mobile devices and the Internet for independent learning outside of classes have a positive effect

on expanding their knowledge. They want to have access to educational resources at any time. Mobile learning has many advantages: when students gain access to educational information and systems via mobile communications, this technology can significantly improve and enrich the learning process itself.

Mobile users use mobile devices to meet their information needs by reading news on various topics, watching videos, live broadcasts and exclusive shows, as well as information on commercial platforms, installing mobile applications on the device. To do this, first of all, you need to install mobile applications on the device via the Internet.

It is universally accepted that the organization of the educational process can be divided into traditional, technological and multimedia levels. At the traditional level, communication between the teacher and the student is always ensured. Therefore, it is necessary to constantly monitor the level of knowledge acquisition and the formation of practical skills, as well as promptly identify and correct errors. The technological level of education quality determines the presence of many information channels in education, which significantly accelerates its development and consolidation. In the educational process, more and more attention is paid to teaching. This involves the use of oral teaching, television, personal computers, technical means and the entire complex of training. Over the past few years, the Department of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science of Karshi State University has been conducting methodological work on organizing independent student learning in the LMS Moodle system, based on the integration of interaction with secondary educational institutions.

Moodle (an abbreviation for Modular Object Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) is a powerful pedagogical software package for organizing training and online classes in a web environment. The founder and developer of the Moodle electronic course management system is Martin Dougiamas, who has been implementing a number of projects to develop the system since 1999. Version 1.0 of the system was developed on August 20, 2002. Version 3.1 of the system is currently widely used.

The introduction of independent learning for high school students in comprehensive schools based on the proposed mobile technology will ensure full mastery of the subject "Computer Science and Information Technology" in the educational process and the integration of various organizational forms of training, improving the quality of education and continuity of training.

Developing an exercise to highlight students' independent work using the example of the subject of native language

Subject name: Native language

Subject name: Consolidation. Work on text and vocabulary.

Lesson objectives:

a) educational objective: to consolidate the acquired knowledge on the topic of "Simple and complex sentences", to develop the skills and abilities of identifying simple and complex sentences in the text, as well as the means of their connection.

b) educational objective: to cultivate the spiritual and moral qualities of students.

c) developmental objective: to develop students' scientific worldview, thinking, oral and written skills, teach them to think freely, find solutions in problem situations, enrich their knowledge and skills in complex sentences.

Expected lesson results: after mastering the topic, students will acquire the following knowledge and skills:

1. Have an idea of a complex sentence and its types in the Uzbek literary language.
2. Understand that parts of a complex sentence are connected by equal conjunctions.
3. They will receive information about the role of complex sentences in our language.
4. They will see in practice the use of complex sentences based on various practical and theoretical tasks and exercises.

Lesson type: mixed.

Teaching methods and technologies: conversation, the "Conceptual Analysis" method, the "Diary" method, the "Brainstorming" method, explanation, demonstration, example, oral and written presentation (debate), various drawings, the "Pisa Test" method.

Teaching forms: work in small groups using slides.

Teaching method: based on games and tasks, tests and exercises.

Assessment methods: motivation and assessment.

Information sources and technical means: computer, projector, screen, slide, teaching and handouts, PISA test, colored and white paper, markers.

Lesson type: theoretical and practical.

Time allotted for the lesson: 45 minutes.

Lesson progress.

I. Organizational part. (5 minutes)

WHAT OBJECTIVES SHOULD WE SET FOR EFFECTIVE TRAINING? • *Listening attentively*
• *Learning attentively* • *Active participation* • *Mutual respect and solidarity* • *Effective results* • *Final conclusion*

- a) greeting students;
- b) preparing students for the lesson;
- c) determining attendance;
- d) announcing the lesson motto and wisdom of the day, discussing them.

✓ **Lesson motto:** *A merged river is a river, a scattered stream is a stream.*

(Uzbek folk proverb)

✓ **Wisdom of the day:** *A man without knowledge is like a barren tree, Knowledge is the delight of the world.*

Abdullah Avloni

II. Assignment and assessment of homework. (10 minutes)

1. Students are divided into groups and given names.

Group I: "Knowledgeable" Group II: "Smart" Group III: "Inventive"

2. The "Analysis of concepts" method is used. Group leaders write down definitions corresponding to the presented concepts in a table.

Method "Analysis of concepts".

Concepts	Content
Simple sentence	
Compound sentence	
Conjunctions	
Classification of compound sentences	
Equal connectors	
Connecting links	

Pisa test. The knowledge of all three groups is tested through the Pisa test:

Topic: Compound Sentences and Their Conjunctions page:17
Autumn has come and the harvest has begun. Find the conjunction of these compound sentences.
A) auxiliary device
B) preposition
C) equal conjunction
D) relative clause

Topic: Simple and compound sentences. page:15
The bleating of sheep could be heard from the fields. What kind of sentence is it according to its structure?
A) compound sentence
B) Simple sentence
C) compound sentence with a subordinate clause
D) compound sentence without a conjunction

Topic: Information about compound sentences page:22
What is a compound sentence that is connected by equal parts using conjunctions?
A) subordinate clause
B) subordinate clause
C) compound clause
D) compound clause without conjunction

III. Presentation of a new topic. (15 minutes)

1. Students are given a topic. The new topic is explained using slides.

2. Theoretical information on the topic is given, examples are given.

2. Working with the overhead projector.

The study of the new topic continues in an interactive mode. First, a “brainstorming” session is organized based on the first task in the textbook.

Brainstorming. What parts is this story divided into?

Then the lights went out, and suddenly a shot rang out. (Abdullah Kahhor)

Observation. Students divide sentences into parts based on their previous knowledge.

Solution. These sentences are divided into parts, as in the example.

Example: *Then the lights went out, and suddenly a shot rang out.* (Abdullah Kahhor) The sentence consists of the following parts: the first sentence is “Then the lights went out”; the second sentence is “Suddenly a shot rang out”.

Students answer the teacher's question: "What type of sentences do the above sentences belong to in terms of the number of punctuation marks?" - a conclusion is made based on the question, based on the content of the task.

Conclusion. The above sentences are complex, formed by the grammatical and content connection of two or more simple sentences.

Then the teacher organizes another "brainstorming" on task 2.

"Brainstorming". What means of communication are used to connect the parts of the above sentences?

Analysis and solution. Students analyze the above sentences and come to the following conclusion: the above complex sentences are connected with each other using members and equal conjunctions, the suffix -u and the word esa. Then the teacher organizes another "brainstorming" on the next question.

Brainstorming. What types of complex sentences are sentences connected with the help of equal conjunctions, the words bolse, esa, bolmasa and the suffixes -u(-yu), -da?

Students answer the questions. The teacher, based on the generalization of their answers, explains the following from the new topic:

Sentences in which the members are equal conjunctions, and the words if, and According to the task of exercise 53, students determine the means of communication and types of complex sentences in these sentences. Example: *Umrlar o`tar-u, kitob yashar.* (Gafur Gulom). This sentence is a complex sentence with the ending -u.

On the slide, students are shown different pictures. Students make sentences based on the pictures and find related complex sentences in the sentences.

Based on the tasks completed by the students independently and on the board, all ideas are generalized and a conclusion is made.

IV. Consolidation of the new topic. (10 minutes)

"Diary" technology.

In this case, students are divided into two groups. The first group writes simple sentences in the first part of the table. The second group writes parts of a complex sentence that continue the meaning of these sentences. The results of the first group are assessed by whether they wrote simple sentences correctly, and the second group - by whether they correctly transformed these sentences into compound ones.

Part I	Part II
Suddenly the door opened with a bang	and Eltojev appeared on the threshold

Gulchehra laughed loudly and	reached out to pick up the knot
She returned to her room and	began to think
At that moment the light went out	Suddenly a shot rang out

V. Assessment of students. (3 minutes)

At the end of the lesson, students who actively participated in the lesson are **assessed, and a discussion of the topic of autumn is held on the following questions:**

What season is called autumn?

What is autumn nature?

What color is the environment in autumn?

How do poets describe autumn?

VI. Homework and conclusion of the lesson. (2 minutes)

The teacher concludes the conversation and assigns **homework:** compose a text on the topic "**Autumn landscapes**" using coherent sentences from exercise 56.

Technological map of the lesson

№	Qualification requirements	<p>Knowledge: Information about connected sentences. Knowledge is acquired on the topic.</p> <p>Skills: The ability to apply knowledge in familiar situations is formed based on exercises and tasks</p> <p>Competence: Can apply the acquired skills in unfamiliar situations.</p> <p>Competence: Can understand, read the text following the rules of orthoepy, can follow the rules of spelling, can use it in familiar and unfamiliar situations and distinguish between them.</p>
	<i>Goals and objectives</i>	<p>-To provide students with theoretical information on a new topic.</p> <p>-To educate students in the spirit of patriotism, to form a sense of camaraderie.</p> <p>-To develop students' independent thinking skills, improve oral and written speech</p> <p>To arouse students' interest in the topic, to expand their knowledge.</p>
	The content of the learning process	<i>Students</i>

	Technology of implementing the educational process	Method: Practical, theoretical, mixed, unconventional, traditional Method: "concept analysis", "Daily", "Brainstorming", questions and answers, group work Form: individual and group work Tools: Textbook? Tests? Tables, audio and video materials, didactic and handout materials Control: Oral, written question and answer test. Evaluation: Based on a 5-point system
	Expected result	Teacher: I achieve that students master the subject in a short time, increase student activity, arouse students' interest in science, teach students to independently learn and memorize, to be able to convey information to others, to ask questions and answer questions correctly. Student: Students acquire knowledge and skills on the subject, are able to think independently, develop their speech, and acquire information in a short time
	Future plans	Teacher: To master and apply pedagogical technologies in the lesson, to improve them, to learn ways to effectively use ICT tools, to work on oneself. Student: To conduct independent research, to conduct research, to learn to express one's opinion competently and to respect the opinions of friends, to try to find additional materials on the topic, to study them. To form the skills of working together in a friendly environment
	Homework	Exercise 56

CONCLUSION.

It is becoming increasingly apparent that the effectiveness of training is achieved through the use of new pedagogical and information technologies in organizing independent work of students in comprehensive schools. It is necessary to involve electronic educational resources and competently design the lesson. The perfection of lesson development is a factor in the development of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students.

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